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**Situational and daily
technology use and
wellbeing among
adolescents.
A report on the findings
from an ESM study
conducted in Belgium
and Finland**

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Situational and daily technology use and wellbeing among adolescents

A report on the findings from an ESM study conducted in
Belgium and Finland

Work Package 5 – Deliverable 5.4

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Executive summary

This report presents the findings from an **experience sampling method (ESM) study** conducted in **Belgium and Finland**. The aim of this study was to examine adolescents' **situational and daily information and communications technology (ICT) use** and its associations with **wellbeing**.

In both countries, the study was conducted in two waves, during the early and late autumn 2022, respectively. In addition, a supplementary data collection was carried out in Finland in spring 2023. The data consists of **17,671 momentary and daily questionnaire responses** from **456 participants**. The participants were 13- to 17-year-old adolescents (63% girls) from seven different schools.

ESM, a momentary survey method, was used to collect data *in situ* with participants' mobile phones. Four momentary and two diary questionnaires were administered during the 14-day data collection period in each wave. The method allows assessing experiences and behaviour that are situational and context-specific, reducing retrospective bias. Moreover, ESM allowed collecting data from a variety of topics by administering both momentary and daily questionnaires.

The study was concerned with assessing adolescents' **specific forms of technology use**, such as interacting with others by messaging or browsing websites, rather than focusing on screentime or use of specific apps. Additionally, the psychological wellbeing of participants was examined by assessing their **affective states**. Participants were also requested to report on their **sleep** daily. Other topics of interest were daily online experiences and activities related to news and comments, problematic social media use, self-determination in ICT use, and face-to-face interaction.

Key findings:

- Participants reported frequent engagement with technology, particularly browsing social media and messaging. Passive use, such as browsing, was more common than active interaction and creation. Adolescents often engaged in multiple activities simultaneously while using technology.
- The situational, within-person associations between technology use and emotions were small. Most effects found were negligible (i.e., smaller than the smallest effect size of interest), but a small relationship was found between watching videos and increased relaxation.
- Results on between-person level indicated that more frequent ICT use was related to higher average levels of boredom and loneliness along with less relaxation. From specific types of technology use, browsing social media and websites more often was related to higher levels of boredom and tiredness. Moreover, frequent social media browsing was also linked with feelings of loneliness, whereas listening to music was associated with boredom, loneliness, and frustration.
- The daily within-level effects between technology use and sleep were also small. Adolescents reported going to bed later, sleeping for shorter durations and having lower quality sleep when doing homework right before bedtime.
- Between-level correlations revealed that spending time with family before bed more often was related to better and longer sleep over the research period. Moreover, adolescents who reported using phone in bed and browsing social media and websites more slept less overall.

- Adolescents rarely shared news items or encountered suspected fake news. Reading online comments was more common, with offensive comments being encountered somewhat frequently. Problematic social media used was infrequently reported but still prevalent to some extent among nearly one-fifth of the adolescents.
- Adolescents reported a moderate sense of self-determination in their daily ICT use, with a sense of importance and belongingness. Additionally, adolescents reported engaging in face-to-face interaction with friends outside of school on approximately half of the days.

These findings provide valuable insights into adolescents' daily and situational experiences using technology and online interactions, highlighting both positive and negative aspects and associations with wellbeing. Notably, the associations between ICT use and wellbeing are dependent on the specific uses of technology. However, the effects on within-person level seem to be small or negligible. More work is needed to examine these within-person effects to uncover the possible complex and dynamic nature of, as well as individual differences in, these associations. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the significance of separating within- and between-person effects and examining short-term and long-term impacts of technology use separately. The results of this study, integrated with other findings from the ySKILLS project, help better understand the complex effects that technology has in adolescents' daily life and wellbeing, offering valuable guidance for the development of guidelines and educational programs.

1 Introduction

1.1 The ySKILLS project

The ySKILLS (Youth Skills) project is funded by the European Union (EU's) Horizon 2020 programme. It involves 16 partners from 13 countries to enhance and maximise the long-term positive impact of the information and communications technology (ICT) environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for children and young people by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills. Starting from the view that children are **active agents in their own development**, ySKILLS examines how digital skills mediate the risks and opportunities related to ICT use by 12- to 17-year-olds in Europe (see <https://yskills.eu>).

The overarching aim of ySKILLS

To enhance and maximise the long-term positive impact of the ICT environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for all children by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills.

In the ySKILLS project the aim is to **identify the actors and factors** that undermine or can promote **children's wellbeing** in a digital age. The relations between ICT use and wellbeing are critically and empirically examined over time.

ySKILLS' research objectives

To acquire extensive knowledge and better measurement of digital skills.

To develop and test an innovative, evidence-based explanatory and foresight model predicting the complex impacts of ICT use and digital skills on children's cognitive, physical, psychological and social wellbeing.

To explain how at-risk children (as regards their mental health, ethnic or cultural origin, socioeconomic status and gender) can benefit from online opportunities despite their risk factors (material, social, psychological).

To generate insightful evidence-based recommendations and strategies for key stakeholder groups in order to promote European children's digital skills and wellbeing.

1.2 This report

This report contributes to achieving the second objective of ySKILLS, namely developing an evidence-based model predicting how ICT use impacts children's wellbeing. More specifically, this report presents the results of an experience sampling study, where adolescents' technology use and wellbeing were measured daily and in different situations using mobile devices during two consecutive weeks.

The results from this report continue to develop the conceptual model proposed by the ySKILLS (see **Figure 1**) by capturing situations in which adolescents' use ICT and by examining their wellbeing and experiences in these situations. Therefore, this report examines the short-term effects of ICT use on cognitive wellbeing, measured with experience sampling method (ESM).

Figure 1 ySKILLS conceptual model.

2 Background

Adolescents use ICT frequently in their everyday lives. How technology is used and how much may have an impact on adolescents' overall wellbeing. In this report, we examine adolescents' daily and momentary experiences of ICT use and how it relates to their psychological (i.e., emotions), physical (i.e., sleep), and social (i.e., loneliness) wellbeing.

Both positive and negative emotions are important when considering wellbeing (Eid & Diener, 2004). Positive emotions, such as happiness and enthusiasm, and the absence of negative emotions, such as sadness and anxiety, contribute to greater overall happiness and life satisfaction (Diener, 2000). The relationships between ICT use and emotions, both positive and negative, are likely dependent on the specific activities adolescents engage in, as well as contextual factors. Moreover, emotions are relatively short-lived (e.g., Scherer, 2005; Verduyn et al., 2009) and susceptible to retrospective bias (Robinson & Clore, 2002). Therefore, they are difficult to assess using traditional survey methods.

Another key aspect to consider in adolescents' wellbeing is sleep. Most adolescents use some form of digital media before going to bed (Gradisar et al., 2013). Previous cross-sectional research suggests that technology use is associated with later bedtimes and problems falling asleep (Lund et al., 2021), which are detrimental to adolescents' wellbeing in many ways. However, contrary to these cross-sectional findings, an experience sampling study by Das-Friebel and colleagues (2020) showed that social media use is not detrimental on a daily level to objectively measured sleep or following day self-reported affective well-being of young adults. Furthermore, the type of social media use moderates its effects on sleep (Scott & Woods, 2019). A recent cross-national study from 18 European and North American countries suggested that problematic social media use is more harmful for sleep and later bedtimes than so called normative social media use (Boniel-Nissim et al., 2023). Further, using ICT has different effects on sleep in different age groups among adolescents (Maksniemi et al., 2022). The present study builds on this work measuring sleep duration and subjective sleep quality repeatedly early in the morning for more accurate assessments.

Previous research on adolescents' technology use and its correlates relies mostly on cross-sectional studies (Science Advice Initiative of Finland, 2021; Hietajarvi et al., 2022). While these studies offer valuable insights, their cross-sectional design limits their ability to uncover both the immediate impacts of digital media use and the long-term developmental processes involved. Importantly, short- and long-term effects of technology use can differ or even be opposite (Smahel et al., 2022). To address this gap, our study uses momentary measures to focus specifically on the short-term processes related to adolescents' technology use and wellbeing.

Experience sampling method (ESM; Hektner et al., 2007) is a research method that involves collecting momentary survey data using mobile devices. This approach offers several advantages (e.g., Salmela-Aro et al., 2017). First, it enables the assessment of behaviour and experiences that are situation- or context-specific. Second, the ESM surveys are administered in real-time, minimizing the potential for retrospective bias. Third, the data is collected within authentic real-world settings, increasing its ecological validity. Fourth, by obtaining repeated measures from individuals, the reliability of the data is increased. Lastly, ESM allows disentangling of within-person (i.e., intraindividual) and between-person (i.e., inter-individual) processes (see e.g., Hamaker, 2012). By focusing on within-person processes, researchers can explore variation within individuals over time and across situations, rather than solely examining on differences between individuals. This temporal perspective also enables the investigation of directionality of effects, which is an important step in understanding potential causal relationships.

3 Aims

The primary aim of the current research is to examine the short-term effects of technology use on adolescents' wellbeing, specifically, their psychological wellbeing (e.g., emotions) and sleep (facet of physical wellbeing). To gain better understanding on these associations, it is important to consider the specific goals or nature of the activities adolescents engage in, rather than focusing solely on the technology or app itself. The effects of ICT can be viewed as either risky or beneficial, depending on specific activities and the situations in which they occur (Mascheroni et al., 2020). For example, active online activities (i.e., activities focusing on interaction) may have different influences on wellbeing compared to passive activities like browsing (Valkenburg et al., 2022; Verduyn et al., 2017). Moreover, adolescents' pre-existing conditions and experiences are expected to moderate daily associations between ICT use and wellbeing (Valkenburg & Peter, 2013). Furthermore, the relationships between technology use and wellbeing may vary depending on whether we examine the within- or between-person effects (e.g., Maksniemi et al., 2022; Puukko et al., 2020). For instance, browsing social media may offer temporary respite and relaxation in the immediate moment but have different long-term outcomes if it becomes pervasive in adolescents' daily lives. Accordingly, this research aims to address the following objectives:

1. Investigate the situational relationships between technology use and affective states. In other words, we are interested in how different forms of technology use is associated with adolescents' emotional wellbeing, encompassing both positive and negative affective states, across various situations and contexts.
2. To examine how ICT use before sleep relates to self-reported bedtime, sleep duration, and sleep quality on a daily level and between adolescents.
3. To explore adolescents' daily online experiences and activities related to news consumption, online commenting, problematic social media use, self-determination of technology use, and frequency of face-to-face interaction with peers.

When investigating the first two research questions, we are interested in both intraindividual (i.e., within-person) and interindividual (i.e., between-person) relationships. These two levels help us answer two different research questions. By analysing intraindividual effects, we can examine how an individual's technology use behaviour is associated with changes in their wellbeing on a situational basis. In contrast, interindividual relationships pertain to the rank-order differences between individuals. For instance, interindividual association between browsing websites and boredom would indicate that more frequent browsing of websites is linked to higher average levels of boredom.

4 Methodology

4.1 Procedure

Data collection for this study was conducted in two waves in both countries Finland and Belgium, taking place in August–September 2022 and November 2022, respectively. Additionally, supplementary data collection in Finland took place between February and March 2023. It is important to note that the original onset of the study was delayed due to the impact of COVID-19. The research and data collection design were developed in collaboration with schools and received approval by the Research Ethics Committee in the Humanities and Social and Behavioural Sciences of University of Helsinki, Finland, as well as the Social and Societal Ethics Committee of the KU Leuven, Belgium (G-2022-5099-R2(MAR)).

The study commenced with a kick-off event, during which participants received instructions on how to install the m-Path application on their mobile phones in Google Play or App Store. The m-Path application, developed by the University of KU Leuven (Mestdagh et al., 2022), is a GDPR-compliant tool specifically designed for administering momentary surveys. Participants were also provided guidance on how to respond to ESM questionnaires using the application. In Belgium, participants additionally completed a background questionnaire including socio-demographic characteristics and the [youth Digital Skills Indicator](#) (yDSI; see Helsper et al., 2020), while the Finnish participants were included in the target sample for the three-wave ySKILLS longitudinal survey conducted in six European countries in 2021–2023 with 12- to 18-year-old children (see <https://yskills.eu/>).

Throughout the two-week data collection, participants were requested to complete six daily questionnaires. Four of the questionnaires were designed to capture participants' momentary experiences of both digital device usage and their affective states. The questionnaires were administered at random times from 9:00 to 21:00. The remaining two questionnaires were both administered once per day, in the morning (at 7:00) and evening (at 21:15), respectively. The morning questionnaire assessed participants' sleep and their activities from the previous evening, while the evening questionnaire prompted participants to reflect on their ICT-related experiences during the day. For a more detailed description of the data collection procedure, please refer to the [ySKILLS D4.5 report](#) (Salmela-Aro et al., 2022).

4.2 Data and sample

The ESM data encompasses a total of 17,671 responses provided by 456 Finnish and Belgian adolescents ($M_{\text{age}} = 15.1$ years; 63% girls, 35% boys, 2% other). Girls were slightly overrepresented in the sample compared to the population—four percentage points in the Finnish data and eight in the Belgian data (Flemish Ministry of Education and Training, 2023; Vipunen – Education Statistics Finland, 2022). However, gender differences favouring females are consistently observed in survey studies (Becker, 2022).

An overview of the participant sample is presented in **Table 1**. In the Belgian sample, 296 adolescents gave their consent for the study, with one declining to participate. However, 44 adolescents dropped out of the study before responding to an ESM questionnaire. In the Finnish sample, 225 provided their consent, while 8 declined and 21 did not respond to any questionnaires after their consent. The participants were selected from seven different secondary schools. The Belgian sample consisted of students in the third to sixth grade of secondary school (aged 13 to 17 years) from four schools, whereas the Finnish sample included first-year upper secondary school students (aged 15 to 16 years) from three schools. The average self-reported socioeconomic status (SES) was 3.87, indicating a

relatively high level of wellbeing on a five-point scale (ranging from 1 *We struggle* to 5 *We live very well*).

Table 1 Participant sample statistics.

	Belgium	Finland	Total
Participants	252	204	456
Responses	8,699	8,972	17,671
Schools	4	3	7
Girls	64%	61%	63%
Average age	14.7	15.8	15.1
Average SES*	3.99	3.67	3.87

Note. Self-reported SES with five categories: 1 *We struggle*, 2, *We live modestly*, 3 *We live ok*, 4 *We live well*, 5 *We live very well*.

Table 2 displays the number of participants and responses for each wave of data collection in both countries. The first wave comprises 9,577 responses, the second wave includes 6,477 responses, and an additional 1,617 responses were collected during the supplementary data collection in Finland. These responses are distributed among the three questionnaire types as follows: 10,821 responses for the momentary questionnaire, 3,762 responses for the morning questionnaire, and 3,088 responses for the evening questionnaire. The intent was to recruit same participants in the second wave that participated in the first wave. However, recruiting the adolescents in both waves proved to be difficult. In Belgium, 85 participated in both waves providing 5,808 responses, whereas in Finland, 86 participants participated in both waves providing 5,494 responses. Due to the difficulties in recruiting, participants in the third (supplementary) wave were asked to participate in only one wave of data collection.

Table 2 Number of participants and responses in each wave.

	Wave 1	Wave 2	Wave 3	Total
<i>Belgian sample</i>				
Participants	251	86		252
Responses	7,074	1,625		8,699
Compliance rate	61.6%	57.8%		60.9%
<i>Finnish sample</i>				
Participants	129	120	42	204
Responses	2,503	4,852	1,617	8,972
Compliance rate	41.2%	69.3%	68.9%	61.4%
<i>Total sample</i>				
Participants	380	206	42	456
Responses	9,577	6,477	1,617	17,671
Compliance rate	56.3%	66.4%	66.9%	61.2%

Note. Compliance was averaged over groups and includes participants that started the study (i.e., provided at least one response).

4.3 Measures

The measures employed in this study were designed to capture both situational ICT use and affective states through momentary questionnaires, as well as daily ICT use and wellbeing through diary

questionnaires. Some of the scales, such as those assessing state emotions, have been used in previous ESM studies (see J. Inkinen et al., 2020; Järvinen et al., 2022; Ketonen et al., 2023). Back-translation was not employed, but the consistency of the items in both languages was ensured by translating the scales into English and having them reviewed by a native researcher. Additionally, alongside the ESM questionnaires, ySKILLS longitudinal survey (Finnish sample) and a background questionnaire (Belgian sample) were used to describe the gender, age, and SES of the participants. For detailed descriptions of the scales, please refer to Appendices A to D and the [ySKILLS report D4.5](#) (Salmela-Aro et al., 2022).

4.3.1 Momentary measures

The momentary questionnaire was designed to assess participants' ICT use, its context, and affective states. The participants were asked to indicate, whether they were in class, in school but not in class, on their free time/out of school, or doing something else. *Technology use* was assessed with the question: "Were you using any technology or device?" If the participant responded with "Yes" they were presented with a multiple-choice follow-up question to assess the specific form of technology use. The response categories, which participants were allowed to choose multiple options from, included messaging others, browsing social media, and browsing websites, among others. The questionnaire also included follow-up items (e.g., social media platform, the content of websites they browsed and whether they shared self-created content) based on the participant's selected response categories. Finally, *affective states* were measured using PANAS-type scales (Watson & Tellegen, 1988), where participants were asked to rate on a scale from 1 (*not at all*) to 7 (*very much*) how well each word described their current feelings. Please refer to Appendix B for a comprehensive list of response options and scales.

4.3.2 Daily measures

The daily questionnaire administered in the mornings was aimed to assess participants' pre-bedtime activities, sleep quality, timing, and duration. *Pre-bedtime activity* was assessed using a multiple-choice item: "What did you do during the last 30 minutes before going to sleep?" In addition to the forms of technology use covered in the momentary questionnaire (e.g., messaging), response options included reading, spending time with family, and doing homework. Two items measured phone-use in bed before sleeping and after waking up, respectively. Various aspects of sleep were assessed in the questionnaire, including *ease of falling asleep* ("Did you fall asleep easily?"), *sleep quality* ("How well did you sleep last night?"), *bedtime* ("At what time did you go to sleep?") and *wakeup time* ("At what time did you wake up in the morning?"). Appendix C presents a complete list of response options and scales in the morning questionnaire.

The evening questionnaire was designed to capture various aspects of participants' online activities and experiences. Participants were asked to indicate whether they had shared a news item online during the day, and if so, whether they had read the news item. Moreover, they were asked to select the content category of the news item from multiple-choice options such as politics, economics, and others. Participants were also asked whether they had come across a news item that they suspected to be fake news, specifying the platform and subject category using predefined response options. Additionally, participants indicated if they had read online comments, and selected response categories that described the comments (e.g., funny, offensive). For those reporting offensive comments, further questions were asked about platforms and the targets of the offensive remarks, again using predetermined categories. *Self-determined ICT use* was assessed with four items measuring (competence, autonomy, relatedness and purpose) in terms of learning, meaningfulness, importance, and belongingness (e.g., "Using digital devices today [e.g., mobile phone], I felt that I learned something new"). Participants were asked to respond with a five-point scale ranging from 1

not at all to 5 very much. *Problematic social media use* was evaluated with three items capturing negative emotions, conflicts with others, and dishonesty related to social media use using a five-point scale. Lastly, participants estimated the amount of face-to-face time they spent with their friends outside of school. For a detailed overview of the questionnaire items, please refer to Appendix D.

4.4 Data analysis

The ESM data consists of repeated measures from each participant and are organized in a hierarchical way with moments (and diary responses) nested within individuals. Accordingly, we used multilevel analytical approach in analysing the data (see e.g., Muthén & Asparouhov, 2010), partitioning the within- and between-person effects in models (Hamaker, 2012) and controlling for systematic error caused by the nestedness of the data. This allows for making inferences about the intraindividual (i.e., within-person) relationships between the variables. In other words, we examined how technology use was related to situational deviations from the participants' subjective "baselines" in affective states, among other variables. By examining the interindividual (i.e., between-person) relationships, we can also examine trends in these relationships and identify more constant effects. All statistical analysis were conducted using R and Mplus Version 8.9 (Muthén & Muthén, 1998–2018). Full information maximum likelihood estimator (FIML) was used to handle missing data. Although, the amount of missing values was low (< 1%) as skipping was not allowed in most of the items in the questionnaires.

Before the analysis, the data were screened and processed using R statistical programming language (R Core Team, 2022). For a detailed description of how the data was processed, please refer to [ySKILLS report D4.5](#) (Salmela-Aro et al., 2022). We identified outliers that were removed from the data. For example, some responses included bedtimes that were later than wakeup times. The affective variables were centred within person (centered within cluster; CWC) before examining their intraindividual associations with technology use, and person means were used when examining interindividual associations. Moreover, bedtime and wakeup time were centred at midnight using hours as units. Sleep-related variables were treated similarly to affective variables when assessing within- and between-level correlations. Furthermore, participants with less than five ESM responses were excluded from the analysis when examining the momentary associations between technology use and affective states, resulting in a data set of 10,578 data points from 344 participants. When analysing the daily associations between pre-bedtime activity and sleep, the cut-off criterion was set to three responses at minimum, resulting in 3,616 responses from 329 adolescents. We used the "complex" option in Mplus to calculate statistical significance (p values) of the correlations in order to control for systematic error caused by nestedness in the data.

5 Results

5.1 Situational technology use and affective states

5.1.1 Technology use in situations

Participants used a technology or a digital device in 48% of the situations during which they responded to the questionnaires. Among the reported types of technology use (see **Figure 2**) browsing social media (35%) was the most common, followed by messaging (19%). Watching videos (13%), listening to music (11%), and playing games (11%) were also frequently reported, while browsing websites occurred in 6% of the situations and content creation in on 2%. Additionally, in 22% of all reports, adolescents selected the category “Something else, what?”. The open-ended responses following this option consisted in large part of study-related activities (e.g., “I studied”). Overall, the findings suggest that reported technology use was more skewed towards passive use such as browsing and consuming content, rather than active use such as interacting with others or creating content. Within the situations involving ICT multitasking, which accounted for 15% of the total responses, participants reported simultaneous messaging and browsing social media in 59% of cases.

Figure 2 Types of technology use.

Figure 3 presents the differences between boys and girls in how frequently they engaged in different types of technology use. Girls reported browsing social media, messaging, and creating content more often when compared to boys. Boys reported gaming more frequently. These differences were not unexpected and similar results are reported in previous studies (Blahošová et al., 2023; Smahel et al., 2020). The comparison was limited to differences between boys and girls due to low number of participants not identifying with these genders (n = 7).

Figure 3 Gender differences in the proportion of the forms of technology based on weighted means. 95% confidence interval (CI) for the means was calculated by bootstrapping 1,000 draws.

The types of technology use varied across different situations (see **Figure 4**). Adolescents reported using technology almost as frequently during class (49%) as they did during their free time (50%), but the forms of use were different. However, when the adolescents were in school but not in class, the reported use of digital device was lower (38%). Browsing social media emerged as the most common activity reported by adolescents in situations when they were in school but not in class (41%), during their free time or when not in school (40%), and in other situations (41%). During class, the most common activity was “something else” (52%) which, based on the open-ended reports, often pertained to studying. Participants reported less social media use, messaging, and listening to music, but more browsing and other types of use (including study-related use) while in class than in their free time.

Participants reported using TikTok in 60% of the situations when they browsed social media, highlighting its popularity among adolescents. Snapchat and Instagram were also widely used, with 35% and 34% of the captured situations involving these platforms, respectively. YouTube emerged as the preferred platform in 18% of the captured situations, while Facebook was rarely browsed (2%). It is worth noting that participants commonly engaged with multiple social media platforms simultaneously, with 30% of the social media use situations involving the use of multiple platforms concurrently.

Figure 4 Different forms of technology use across activity. SOME = “Browsing social media”. Percentage represents proportion of technology use type within each activity class. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals for proportions.

5.1.2 Affective states

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics for the affective variables. The data reveals that among these variables, participants reported the highest levels of tiredness and the lowest levels of loneliness across the situations. Intraclass correlations (ICC) indicate the extent of variability in a variable that can be attributed to differences between individuals (i.e., interindividual or between-person differences). Among the affective variables, anxiety, and restlessness exhibited the highest ICC value of .48, indicating that 48% of the variance is attributable to differences between individuals, while 52% of the variance is related to situational. On the other hand, boredom shows the highest degree of situational variability among the variables, with an ICC of .34.

Table 3 Descriptive statistics of affective variables.

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>Skew</i>	<i>Kurtosis</i>	<i>ICC</i>
Tiredness	3.61	1.87	1	7	0.18	-1.01	.37
Enthusiasm	3.29	1.83	1	7	0.44	-0.79	.45
Relaxation	3.29	1.83	1	7	0.44	-0.80	.39
Boredom	2.90	1.80	1	7	0.70	-0.49	.34
Stress	2.73	1.74	1	7	0.85	-0.23	.43
Frustration	2.48	1.71	1	7	1.08	0.23	.37
Restlessness	2.23	1.58	1	7	1.31	0.98	.48
Anxiety	2.07	1.49	1	7	1.55	1.78	.48
Loneliness	1.98	1.46	1	7	1.64	2.08	.43

5.1.3 Associations between technology use and affective states

The correlation heat map in **Figure 5** visually represents the situational associations between technology use and affective states. These associations reflect the average change in participants' affective states from their subjective baseline (i.e., the average over the entire measurement period) when engaging in specific types of digital technology use. We found few statistically significant but small associations. Specifically, despite small statistically significant association only the within-person correlation between watching videos and relaxation exceeded the commonly used smallest effect size of interest (SESOI) of .1 (e.g., Orben, 2020), which would indicate that 1% of the variation in the affective state could be accounted for variation in media use. Effects smaller than SESOI are negligible.

Figure 5 Situational within-level correlations between ICT use and affective variables. *SOME* = browsing social media. Affective variables 10–18 are centered within subjects. Binary technology use variables 1–9 are not centered. Statistically significant correlations with $p < .05$ are shown with black text and coloured tile, nonsignificant with grey text. The systematic error due to nestedness of the scores were controlled for when calculating the p -values.

Figure 4 also illustrates correlations between different forms of technology use, indicating concurrent activities described earlier. Additionally, it displays associations between different affective states. Generally, positive affect variables displayed positive correlations among themselves, while negative affect variables showed positive correlations with each other. Moreover, positive affect variables exhibited negative correlations with negative affect variables.

Figure 6 displays the correlations between different types of technology use and affective states at the between-person level. These correlations denote the associations between the average scores reported by adolescents throughout the entire measurement period, reflecting more stable individual differences. The findings suggest that adolescents who reported more frequent technology use across situations also reported higher levels of boredom and loneliness, along with lower levels of relaxation. Frequent engagement in browsing social media and websites, as well as listening to music, were similarly associated with increased levels of boredom and tiredness. Similar patterns were observed between social media use and loneliness. Additionally, listening to music was associated with loneliness and frustration.

Figure 6 Between-person correlations between ICT use and affective variables. *SOME* = browsing social media. Statistically significant correlations with $p < .05$ are shown with black text and coloured tile, nonsignificant with grey text.

Also presented in the figure are the correlations between average frequencies of technology use throughout the measurement period. Adolescents who reported messaging others frequently also tended to engage in browsing social media and websites, content creation, and listening to music. Content creation displayed positive associations with all forms of ICT use, except for the “other” category. Listening to music showed similar pattern. However, it was associated with gaming and was not related to other use. Notably, strong positive correlations were found between enthusiasm and relaxation, as well as among negative affective states. Furthermore, relaxation displayed a negative relationship with anxiety.

5.2 Sleep and pre-bed activity

Figure 7 presents the frequencies of self-reported activities 30 minutes before going to bed. Browsing social media (34%), sending messages (19%), and watching series, movies or programs (19%), and spending time with family (17%) were the most common activities 30 minutes before adolescents went to bed. In addition, reading a book (11%), listening to music (10%), and doing homework (9%) were somewhat common. Reporting multiple simultaneous activities was common, occurring in 25% of the responses. When reporting multiple activities, adolescents reported most often browsing social media (61%), messaging (45%), spending time with family (34%), and watching videos (32%). Messaging and browsing social media were again a common combination, reported in 31% of the responses that included multitasking.

Figure 7 Self-reported pre-bedtime activity.

The reported use of social media platforms in the evening resembled the usage of the apps in daily situations in terms of the order of popularity: TikTok (69%), Snapchat (53%), and Instagram (44%) were clearly the most popular. YouTube was used in 26% of the situations, whereas Facebook, news sites/platforms, and other apps were each used in 2–3% of the situations.

Table 4 shows the descriptive statistics of self-reported sleep variables measured each morning. Adolescents reported using phone in bed before going to sleep in 57% out of all evenings. In addition, in 41% of the mornings, adolescents reported using phone in bed right after waking up. Adolescents reported falling asleep easily in 82% of the situations and on average reported good sleep quality ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 1.00$). The average bedtime was 22:57 pm before weekdays and 23:41 on Fridays and Saturdays, whereas participants reported waking up 07:00 am on weekdays and 8:59 am during weekends. Average sleep duration was 8 hours 20 minutes ($M = 8.34$, $SD = 1.47$). Adolescents reported 8 hours 2 minutes of sleep on average during nights before weekdays and 9 hours 18 minutes on Friday and Saturday nights. The ICCs indicate that the variation in sleep-related variables was attributable more to the day than individual differences.

Table 4 Descriptive statistics of self-reported sleep variables.

	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>Skew</i>	<i>Kurtosis</i>	<i>ICC</i>
Phone in bed going to sleep	3762	0.57	0.50	0	1	-0.27	-1.93	0.49
Phone in bed waking up	3760	0.41	0.49	0	1	0.36	-1.87	0.48
Fell asleep easily	3762	0.82	0.38	0	1	-1.68	0.81	0.20
Sleep quality	3762	3.89	1.00	1	5	-0.72	0.05	0.38
Sleep time	3674	-0.88	1.34	-7.17	10.43	1.09	3.24	0.47
Wake up time	3674	7.46	1.34	1.5	18.67	1.29	3.18	0.16
Sleep duration	3674	8.34	1.47	1.18	15.83	-0.10	1.76	0.35

Within-person correlations between evening activity categories and sleep variables are illustrated in **Figure 8**. Similarly to the relation between technology use and affective states, some negligible correlations were observed. Only effect exceeding the SESOI of .1 was between homework and sleep duration, indicating that doing homework in the evening was related to less sleep. However, between-person correlations depicted in **Figure 9** showed that adolescents who, on average, reported spending time with their families reported also better sleep quality, earlier bedtimes and longer sleep duration. Using phone before bed more often was associated with the experience of falling asleep easily but also with later bedtime and shorter sleep duration. Listening to music was associated with poorer sleep quality. Messaging and browsing social media were also associated with later bedtimes, and social media browsing was also associated with shorter duration of sleep. Additionally, browsing websites associated negatively with sleep duration.

Figure 8 Within-person correlations between evening activity and sleep variables. *SOME* = Browsing social media, *Phone sleep* = using phone in bed before going to sleep, *Phone wakeup* = using phone in bed after waking up. Sleep variables 12–15 are centered within subjects. Binary evening activity and phone use variables 1–11 are not centered. Statistically significant correlations with $p < .05$ are shown with black text and coloured tile, nonsignificant with grey text.

Figure 9 Between-person correlations between evening activity and sleep variables. *SOME* = browsing social media, *Phone sleep* = using phone in bed before going to sleep, *Phone wakeup* = using phone in bed after waking up. Statistically significant correlations with $p < .05$ are shown with black text and coloured tile, nonsignificant with grey text.

5.3 Daily ICT-related experiences and behaviour

Table 5 shows the descriptive statistics of self-determination in ICT use and problematic social media use. On average, participants reported below the scale mid-point experiences of learning, meaningfulness, importance, and belongingness, suggesting that their daily technology-use was not very self-determined. There was substantial variability both on daily and between-person level, as indicated by ICCs ranging from .44 to .59. Problematic social media use was infrequently reported with mean levels being close to one on a five-point scale (from 1 *not at all* to 5 *very much*). However, when considering the proportion of adolescents who reported a response of four or five on any of the items during the research period, it was found that 18% of the participants fell in this category. Most reported feeling bad (14%), while disagreeing (8%) and lying (9%) about social media use was less common. Furthermore, over than 50% of the variance of problematic social media use was attributed to interindividual differences.

Table 5 Descriptive statistics of self-determination in ICT use and problematic social media use

	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>Skew</i>	<i>Kurt</i>	<i>ICC</i>
<i>Self-determination in ICT use</i>								
Learning	3 088	2.18	0.98	1	5	0.48	-0.46	0.44
Meaningfulness	3 088	2.05	1.03	1	5	0.66	-0.43	0.52
Importance	3 088	2.57	1.14	1	5	0.14	-0.92	0.57
Belongingness	3 088	2.83	1.25	1	5	0.03	-1.03	0.59
<i>Problematic social media use</i>								
Feeling bad	3 088	1.43	0.83	1	5	2.08	3.91	0.58
Arguments	3 088	1.25	0.70	1	5	3.24	11.06	0.61
Lying	3 088	1.21	0.66	1	5	3.63	13.47	0.56

Other questions in the evening questionnaire assessed the frequency of adolescents' online experiences and behaviour in terms of sharing news, reading comments, and encountering potential fake news. The results showed that sharing news items online was rare, being reported only in 8% of the days. However, when they did, the adolescents reported them to be related mostly to politics (22%), entertainment (21%) and health (17%). Adolescents also rarely reported encountering suspected fake news (7%). Conversely, reading online comments was commonly reported (47%). The comments were most often reported to be funny (74%). However, adolescents also encountered informative (37%) and offensive (23%) comments. Offensive comments were most often encountered in TikTok (83%) and Instagram (42%) and were usually targeted at other individuals (86%) rather than the respondent themselves (7%), a group they belong in (e.g., gender, ethnicity; 12%), or another group (14%). Adolescents reported face-to-face interaction with their friends outside of school in half of the days (51%) and often reported daily interaction of more than two hours (22%).

6 Conclusions

6.1 Summary of key findings

The main objective of this study was to examine the situational and daily within-person relationships between adolescents' technology use and wellbeing. The findings revealed interesting between-person associations but very few within-person effects related to affective states and sleep. Further, insights about the frequency of technology use, its different forms, online-related experiences, and behaviour were revealed.

6.1.1 Technology use and affective states

Participants reported frequent engagement with technology, particularly browsing social media and messaging. Passive technology use, such as consuming content, appeared to be more prevalent than active interaction or content creation. TikTok, Snapchat, and Instagram emerged as the preferred social media platforms. Gender differences between boys and girls in technology use was found and these differences were in line with previous research (e.g., Blahošová et al., 2023; Smahel et al., 2020). Messaging, social media use, and content creation were more prevalent among girls, whereas boys reported more gaming.

On situational (within-person) level, the associations between technology use and affective states were mostly negligible. In other words, while they were statistically significant due to the large sample size, the effect sizes were not large enough to be of interest. However, a small effect between watching videos and increased relaxation was observed. The lack of effects may be due to differences in situation or context, such as varying types of content being browsed or watched, aimed to evoke different kinds of reactions. Moreover, there could be individual differences that moderate these effects, which call for further investigation with more precise hypotheses and detailed analysis.

In addition, we observed several between-person level associations, which suggest that there were individual differences that were somewhat stable across the measurement period. However, the effects were small. Adolescents who reported more frequent ICT use also reported higher levels of boredom and loneliness, and lower levels of relaxation. From the specific uses, browsing social media, browsing websites, and listening to music were linked with higher levels of boredom and loneliness over the measurement period. Loneliness was also associated with social media use and music. Furthermore, we did not observe associations between ICT use and enthusiasm on either level. While the lack of associations between technology use and positive emotions is concerning, it is worth noting that we measured fewer positive emotions than negative. Technology use may be linked to other specific positive emotions we did not measure in this study.

The findings highlight the importance of considering the context of technology use as well as separating of within- and between-person effects. The associations between technology use and affective states were small or negligible. However, we found slightly more robust interindividual effects, pointing towards individual differences throughout the measurement period. While these may be indicative of cumulative associations, interpretations about long-term effects cannot be made from this data, as it captures only a small period from the participants lives. In addition, possible individual differences between adolescents in the situational associations are an important consideration. It may be, that the relationships of technology use and affect differ between individuals. Further investigation into underlying mechanisms and individual differences that may moderate these associations is needed.

6.1.2 Pre-bedtime activity and sleep

The results on associations between pre-bedtime activities and sleep are in line with some of the previous findings showing that using technology before bedtime impacts sleep patterns and sleep quality (e.g., Maksniemi et al., 2022). However, the results also showed some nuances in the ways in which different forms of technology use are related to sleep. The most common activities reported 30 minutes before bedtime included browsing social media, sending messages, watching series or movies, and spending time with family. Multiple simultaneous activities were frequently reported, with browsing social media and messaging being the most common combination. Adolescents reported using their phones in bed before going to sleep in most evenings, and often immediately upon waking up in the morning. Participants reported falling asleep easily most of the time and overall had good sleep quality. They reported sleeping over 8 hours per night before weekdays on average and 9 hours 18 minutes per night when the following day was Saturday or Sunday.

The day-to-day within-person associations of pre-bedtime activities and sleep were mostly negligible. There was one small negative effect between doing homework and sleep duration, indicating that when adolescents worked on school assignments before going to bed, they slept for a shorter time. This association was not observed on between-person level. In other words, adolescents who did homework before bedtime more often did not seem to have detrimental effects on their sleep. The within-person effect could be partly explained by having to wake up earlier to go to school, as it is likely that homework is done on evenings before schooldays.

Results on the between-person level indicated that adolescents, who spent time with their family more often before bedtime experienced better sleep quality and slept for longer on average. Using phone in bed before sleep had a detrimental effect on sleep duration. Furthermore, browsing social media and websites more often were related to slightly shorter sleep duration overall.

6.1.3 Daily online experiences and behaviour

The study utilised daily questionnaires to explore adolescents' online experiences and behaviour. The results revealed that negative experiences associated with problematic social media use were relatively rare, yet still prevalent to some extent by 18% of the participants during the research period. Conversely, adolescents reported being able to engage with important things and experience a sense of belongingness somewhat through their use of technology, although experiences related to learning and sense of meaningfulness were less commonly reported.

Adolescents did not frequently share news items or come across news articles that they suspected to be fake. However, reading online comments was a more frequent activity. The majority of comments encountered were most often humorous in nature, but offensive comments were present in 23% of the cases. Notably, TikTok was the platform where offensive comments were most often encountered, aligning with its popularity among adolescents. Additionally, adolescents interacted with their friends face-to-face outside of school on approximately half of the days.

6.2 Strengths and limitations of the study

This study has many strengths but also several limitations that should be acknowledged when interpreting the findings. As a method, ESM reduces the effect of recall bias. However, the self-report questionnaire-based approach may not capture adolescents' technology use objectively. This could be amended using objective screen time logs, which was not possible in this research. However, assessing specific forms or goals of technology use is a strength of this study and difficult to assess without subjective reports. It is also worth noting, that there were difficulties in recruiting participants to the research due to the circumstances of the COVID-19 pandemic and the intensity of the study, which may cause bias. Accordingly, the generalizability of the findings may be limited to the specific demographic characteristics of the sample.

The cross-sectional design prevents making interpretations about causal relationships. For example, an association between boredom and technology use may be due to technology use evoking boredom or adolescents using technology more when they are bored. Future studies should focus on dynamic modelling approach, which allows for more sophisticated analysis of this kind of intensive longitudinal data. Additionally, the study did not extensively explore the influence of individual differences and social factors that may play role. Moreover, the results represent average effects over all participants. There may be variability between individuals and contexts in the relationships, which could also explain the small effects. A more detailed and in-depth analysis is required to examine this variability.

6.3 Recommendations

These findings provide insights into adolescents' daily and situational experiences using technology and in the online realm, highlighting both positive and negative aspects and associations with wellbeing. To advance the knowledge in this field, future research should address the limitations identified in this study. First, studies should examine whether these affects are moderated by context, such as time (e.g., time of day) or activity (e.g., in class vs. free time). Second, it is important to identify individual differences that moderate the effects of technology use on wellbeing, such as demographic (e.g., age, gender) and individual factors (e.g., pre-existing conditions). For example, the effects may differ with individuals that have challenges in emotion regulation or experience loneliness. Third, the temporal effects could be modelled using dynamic analytical approach. These are questions that can be answered, at least partly, with this extensive ySKILLS ESM data set. However, there are also questions outside the scope of this data, such as expanding the sample of participants to a divergent population and examining adolescents at risk.

The findings also have implications for policy making and practice. The results suggest that adolescents who engage more in technology use may be more susceptible to risks for their wellbeing, including negative affect and compromised sleep. However, it is crucial to note that these effects are small and influenced by the specific ways in which adolescents engage with technology. Therefore, promoting responsible technology use that considers the potential on wellbeing is essential. This can be achieved through the development of guidelines and educational programs that emphasize not only the amount of time adolescents spend with their mobile phones, but also the nature of their activities and how they can either support or hinder different aspects of their wellbeing.

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Appendices

A. Appendix 1: Items in longitudinal survey used as background variables

How old are you?

- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15
- 16
- 17
- Older than 17

What is your gender? Please, select which applies...

- Boy
- Girl
- Other

What language(s) do you speak at home most of the time? Select all, which applies.
(list of local languages in each country including the option “other”)

Which of the following best describes your financial situation and that of the people with whom you live?

- We live very well – We can purchase luxury items, like [ADD LOCAL EXAMPLES], and still have money left over
- We live well – We have enough money to afford most things without having to save for them
- We get by ok – We have enough for everyday things, but we have to save for more serious purchases and expenses
- We live modestly – We have to manage our money carefully and limit our daily spending
- We struggle to get by – We sometimes do not have enough money to afford basic needs, such as food and clothes
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

B. Appendix 2: ESM study: Daily questionnaire

Instruction	What were you doing when you got the survey?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I was in class 2. I was in school, but not in class 3. I had free time/not in school 4. Something else, what?

Instruction	Were you using any technology or device?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No

Condition	1. Yes
Instruction	What were you doing specifically? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. communicating with others 2. browsing social media 3. browsing websites (e.g. news, information) 4. watching series/movie/program (e.g. netflix) 5. playing 6. creating pictures/videos/blog texts 7. listening to music 8. something else, what?

Condition	2. browsing social media
Instruction	What social media platform were you using? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tiktok 2. Instagram 3. Snapchat 4. Youtube 5. Facebook 6. Something else, what?

Condition	3. browsing websites (e.g. news, information)
Instruction	What kind of content were you browsing through? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. politics (e.g. war) 2. economics 3. health (e.g. covid19) 4. entertainment, media, art and culture 5. sports 6. something else, what?

Condition	6. I created photos/videos/blogtexts myself
Instruction	Did you share your photos/videos/blogtexts
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No

Condition	1 yes
Instruction	On which social media platform(s)? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tiktok 2. Instagram 3. Snapchat 4. Youtube 5. Facebook 6. some other, what? 7. I don't remember

Instruction	How well do the following words describe your feelings now? At the moment I feel:
Items	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. enthusiastic 2. distressed 3. bored 4. tired 5. anxious 6. relaxed 7. frustrated 8. curious 9. lonely 10. restless
Response options	1 not at all – 7 very much

C. Appendix 3: ESM study: Morning questionnaire

Instruction	What did you do during the last 30 minutes before going to sleep? You can choose multiple options
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I read a book 2. I spent some time with my family 3. I messaged/communicated with others 4. I did schoolwork 5. I browsed social media 6. I browsed websites (e.g., news, information) 7. I created photos/videos/blogtexts myself 8. I watched a series/movie/program (e.g., Netflix) 9. I listened to music 10. something else, what? 11. I don't remember

Condition	5. I browsed social media
Instruction	What social media did you browse? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. TikTok 2. Instagram 3. Snapchat 4. YouTube 5. Facebook 6. news website or app 7. some other, what? 8. I don't remember

Condition	6. I browsed websites (e.g., news, information)
Instruction	What types of websites did you browse? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. politics (e.g. war) 2. economics 3. health (e.g. covid19) 4. entertainment, media, art and culture 5. sports 6. something else, what? 7. I don't remember

Condition	7. I created photos/videos/blogtexts myself
Instruction	Did you share your photos/videos/blogtexts
Response options	1. Yes 2. No

Condition	1. yes
Instruction	On which social media platform(s)? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	1. Tiktok 2. Instagram 3. Snapchat 4. Youtube 5. Facebook 6. some other, what? 7. I don't remember

Instruction	At what time did you go to sleep? (That is, turned off the lights and devices and went to bed, e.g. 22.15)
Response options	Time

Instruction	Did you use your phone in bed right before you started to sleep?
Response options	1. Yes 2. No

Instruction	Did you fall asleep easily?
Response options	1. Yes 2. No

Instruction	How well did you sleep last night?
Response options	1. well 2. quite well 3. moderately 4. quite badly 5. badly

Instruction	At what time did you wake up in the morning?
Response options	Time

Instruction	Did you use your phone in bed immediately as you woke up this morning?
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Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Yes2. No
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D. **Appendix 4: ESM study: Evening questionnaire**

Instruction	Did you share a news item online today?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No 3. I don't remember

Condition	1. Yes
Instruction	Did you read the news item that you shared?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. politics (e.g. war) 2. economics 3. health (e.g. covid19) 4. entertainment, media, art and culture 5. sports 6. something else, what? 7. I don't remember

Condition	1. What was the news item about?
Instruction	Did you read the news item that you shared?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No

Instruction	Have you seen a news item today that made you doubt whether it was real or fake?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No 3. I don't remember

Condition	1. yes
Instruction	Where did you see it?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1 TikTok 2. Instagram 3. Snapchat 4. YouTube 5. Facebook 6. news website or app 7. television 8. radio 9. somewhere else, where? 10. I don't remember

Condition	1. yes
Instruction	What was the fake-news about?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. politics (e.g. war) 2. economics 3. health (e.g. covid19) 4. entertainment, media, art and culture 5. sports 6. something else, what? 7. I don't remember

Instruction	Did you read online comments today?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No 3. I don't remember

Condition	1. yes
Instruction	What types of comments did you encounter? You can choose multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. funny 2. offensive 3. informative 4. other 5. I don't remember/I don't know

Condition	2. offensive
Instruction	Where did you encounter offensive comments? You can choose multiple options:
Response options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 TikTok 2 Instagram 3 Snapchat 4 YouTube 5 Facebook 6 news website or app 7 somewhere else, where? 8 I don't remember

Condition	2. offensive
Instruction	At whom were the offensive comments directed at? You can choose multiple options:
Response options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 me personally 2 some other person 3 the group I belong to or identify with (e.g., gender, ethnicity) 4 a group someone else is part of/identifies with (e.g., gender, ethnicity) 5 I don't know/I'm not sure

Instruction	Using digital devices today (e.g. mobile phone), I felt that I...:
Items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. learned something new? 2. made a difference? 3. got to express myself? 4. was part of a group/collective?
Response options	1 not at all – 5 very much

Instruction	Outside school / in your free time: How much face-to-face -time did you spend with your friends today?
Response options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not at all 2. Less than an hour 3. 1-2 hours 4. more than 2 hours

Instruction	Now think about your social media use today...: During the day, ...
Items	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ...I felt bad when I could not use social media? 2. ...I had arguments with others because of my social media use? 3. ...I lied to my parents or friends about the amount of time I spend on social media?
Response options	1 not at all – 5 very much

Instruction	Please go to your screentime view on your phone settings and indicate here what were and how much time you spent today on the three most used apps:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Most used app 2. Second most used app 3. Third most used app
	Open and Hours and minutes

E. Appendix 5: ESM study: Participant informed consent forms

Finland

Hei lukiolainen

Tulit keväällä 2021 mukaan kansainväliseen nuorten digitaalisen teknologian käyttöä ja hyvinvointia seuraavaan ySKILLS -pitkittäistutkimukseen. Osa tästä tutkimuksesta toteutetaan tänä ja ensi vuonna (2022 ja 2023) nuorten omilla älypuhelimilla ja aktiivisuusrannekeilla. Pyydämme sinua osallistumaan tähän osioon.

Tutkimus pähkinäkuoressa

- Lataat puhelimesi tutkimussovelluksen, joka lähettää useita lyhyitä kysymyssarjoja päivittäin, kahden viikon aikana.
- Aktiivisuusseurantaan osallistuvat käyttävät samanaikaisesti aktiivisuusranneketta vuorokauden ympäri.
- Tutkimuksen jälkeen sovellus poistetaan puhelimesta ja ranneke palautetaan tutkijaryhmälle.

Laajemmin, mitä ja keitä tutkitaan?

ySKILLS on EU:n rahoittama kansainvälinen kolmevuotinen tutkimushanke (2020-2023), jonka tarkoituksena on seurata nuorten kasvua ja kehitystä peruskoulun ja toisen asteen opintojen aikana. Tutkimuksessa kerätään oppilailta kyselylomakkeiden avulla tietoa heidän digiteknologian käytöstä, yleisestä hyvinvoinnista, taustasta sekä kouluarvosanoista.

Älypuhelinsoviossa tutkimme, miten digitaalisen teknologian päivittäinen käyttö heijastuu nuoren tunteisiin, ajatteluun ja hyvinvointiin. Älypuhelinsoviossa lataat m-Path -tutkimussovelluksen puhelimesi (App store/Google play). Sovellus lähettää lyhyitä kysymyssarjoja (kesto n. 1 minuutti) kuudesti päivässä, kahden viikon ajan. Samanaikaisesti osa nuorista pitää aktiivisuusrannekeita (Axivity AX3) aktiivisuuden, vuorokausirytmien ja unen keston arvioimiseksi. Ranneketta tulee pitää koko tutkimusjakson ajan (myös nukkuessa). Ranneketta voi pitää suihkun aikana, mutta halutessaan laitteen saa ottaa pois suihkuun mentäessä. Ranneke tulee ottaa pois myös liikuntaa harrastettaessa, jos liikunta voi vaurioittaa ranneketta tai sen pitäminen on muulla tavoin ongelmallista urheilulajin/käyttäjän kannalta (esim. paini, nyrkkeily, uinti).

Tutkimuksen jälkeen m-Path-sovellus poistetaan puhelimesta ja ranneke palautetaan tutkijaryhmälle. Asiasta on sovittu koulujen ja opettajien kanssa, jotta vastaamisesta aiheutuisi mahdollisimman vähän häiriötä oppilaalle ja muille.

Keräämämme aineisto tuottaa uutta tietoa nuorten digitaalisen teknologian käytön, hyvinvoinnin, tunteiden, ajatusten ja aktiivisuuden yhteyksistä. Tiedon avulla voit oppia tukemaan positiivista kehitystäsi ja sekä vanhemmat että opettajat voivat tukea nuoren positiivista kehitystä. Kaikkia kerättyjä tietoja tutkitaan täysin yleisellä tasolla, pseudonymisoidulla aineistolla, eikä yksittäistä henkilöä voida tunnistaa vastauksista. Tutkimuksen etenemisestä tiedotetaan lukuvuosittain.

Tutkimuksen vapaaehtoisuus, tutkimuksen keskeyttäminen ja suostumuksen peruuttaminen

- Oppilaalla on oikeus milloin tahansa tutkimuksen aikana *keskeyttää* tutkimukseen osallistuminen. Syytä keskeytykselle ei tarvitse ilmoittaa. Tutkimuksesta kieltäytymisellä tai sen keskeyttämisellä ei ole jälkiseurauksia eikä se vaikuta oppilaan kohteluun millään tavalla nyt tai tulevaisuudessa. Keskeytyksen jälkeen oppilaasta ei enää kerätä uutta tietoa, mutta keskeyttämiseen mennessä kerättyjä tietoja käytetään osana tutkimusaineistoa.
- Oppilaan on myös mahdollista *peruuttaa* suostumus tutkimukseen, jolloin kaikki henkilötiedot ja tutkimuksessa kerätty osallistujaa koskeva aineisto poistetaan eikä sitä käytetä tutkimuksen osana. Tutkimuksen keskeyttämisestä tai suostumuksen peruuttamisesta ilmoitetaan tässä kirjeessä yhteyshenkilöksi kirjatulle henkilölle. Kerätty tutkimusaineisto kuitenkin anonymisoidaan syksyllä 2023, minkä jälkeen tietoja ei voida enää poistaa.

Luottamuksellisuus, tietojen käsittely, säilytys ja arkistointi

Tutkimushankkeen tutkijat noudattavat tiukkoja turvallisuusohjeita. Kaikki oppilaiden antamat tiedot ovat ehdottoman luottamuksellisia.

- Nimi ei tule olemaan tulosten tallentamisen jälkeen näkyvissä missään, henkilöllisyys ei käy ilmi tutkimuksen tuloksista eivätkä yksittäisten vastaajien tiedot missään vaiheessa tule kenenkään Helsingin yliopiston ySKILLS-tutkimusryhmän ulkopuolisen tietoon.
- Oppilaan suostumuksella älypuhelimella ja aktiivisuusrannekeella kerättäviä tietoja yhdistetään toisiinsa sekä muuhun ySKILLS-tutkimuksessa hänestä kerättäviin ja jo kerättyihin tietoihin. Näitä tietoja ovat tutkimuksen pitkittäiskyselyaineisto (kevät 2021, 2022 ja 2023) ja oppilaiden arvosanat.
- Kaikkia tutkimusaineistoja käsitellään ja säilytetään tietoturvallisesti EU:n yleisen tietosuojaa-asetuksen sekä tietosuojalain edellyttämällä tavalla. Tutkimuksen aineistoa ja osanottajien uudelleen tavoittamiseksi tarvittavaa nimi- ja yhteystietolistaa säilytetään erillään, jolloin kenenkään yksittäisen osallistujan henkilöllisyys ei paljastu.
- Tutkimusaineistoon ja vastauksiin pääsevät käsiksi vain Helsingin yliopiston ySKILLS-tutkimusryhmän jäsenet. Tutkimusryhmän ulkopuolisten tutkijoiden on myös mahdollista päästä käyttämään tutkimusaineistoa mutta vain läheisessä yhteistyössä ySKILLS-tutkimusryhmän kanssa. Voit kysyä lisätietoja tutkimuksesta tutkijoilta.

Osallistumisesi on tutkimuksen onnistumisen kannalta erittäin tärkeää!

Suomessa tutkimuksesta vastaa akatemiaprofessori Katarina Salmela-Aro Helsingin yliopiston kasvatustieteellisestä tiedekunnasta.

Yhteyshenkilöt ja lisätietoja:

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Englanninkieliset verkkosivut: <https://yskills.eu/>

Päiväys: 17.8.2022

Link: <https://www.oppimisanalytiikka.fi/hankeinfot/yskills/tutkimustiedote/>

Olen lukenut suostumustiedotteen (linkki yllä) ja vahvistan osallistumiseni tähän tutkimukseen sekä hyväksyn antamieni tietojen käyttämisen tutkimustarkoitukseen.

1. Kyllä

2. Ei

NEXT QUESTION

ySkills_Consent

Sallin kerättävän aineiston yhdistämisen muuhun ySKILLS-tutkimuksessa kerättyyn aineistoon.

1. Kyllä

2. Ei

TOESTEMMINGSFORMULIER JONGEREN

Beste jongere,

In het kader van het onderzoeksproject ySKILLS onderzoeken we het verband tussen het gebruik van digitale technologieën en welzijn bij jongeren tussen 12 en 18 jaar. Hieronder geven we een kort overzicht van onze studie:

- Gedurende twee weken krijg je zes keer per dag een paar korte vragen. Op een paar minuten zijn de vragen ingevuld.
- Voor deze studie gebruiken we een smartphone app, m-Path, ontwikkeld aan de KU Leuven. Deze app is conform de huidige privacy wetgeving (AVG). Je installeert de app tijdelijk op je eigen smartphone. De app registreert enkel de antwoorden op de vragen, er worden geen andere (achtergrond)data geregistreerd.
- Deelname aan het onderzoek is volledig anoniem.
- Deelname is vrijwillig en je kunt op elk moment je deelname stopzetten zonder een reden op te geven, en zonder nadelige gevolgen.
- Deze online dagboekstudie zal op twee verschillende momenten plaatsvinden: in september en in november 2022. Het onderzoek loopt parallel ook in Finland.
- Dit lange termijnonderzoek geeft ons unieke inzichten in de mentale gezondheid en dagelijkse activiteiten van jongeren. Op die manier kunnen we betere ondersteuning garanderen voor een positieve ontwikkeling van jongeren.
- Dit onderzoeksproject wordt gefinancierd door de Europese Commissie en heeft ethische goedkeuring gekregen van de Sociaal-Maatschappelijke Ethische Commissie van KU Leuven (goedkeuringsnummer G-2022-5099).
- Als je meer informatie wenst of vragen hebt over deze studie, kan je terecht bij het onderzoeksteam:
 - o Emilie Bossens (email: emilie.bossens@kuleuven.be)
 - o Prof. dr. Leen d'Haenens (email: leen.dhaenens@kuleuven.be)

Je kan akkoord gaan of weigeren om deel te nemen in de studie door dit formulier in te vullen.

- Ik heb de informatie over het ySKILLS online dagboekonderzoek gelezen en **IK WIL DEELNEMEN** aan het online dagboekonderzoek
- IK WIL NIET DEELNEMEN** aan het ySKILLS online dagboekonderzoek

Naam: _____

Voornaam: _____

Plaats en datum: _____

TOESTEMMINGSFORMULIER OUDERS EN VOOGDEN

Beste ouder of voogd,

In het kader van het onderzoeksproject ySKILLS onderzoeken we het verband tussen het gebruik van digitale technologieën en welzijn bij jongeren tussen 12 en 18 jaar. Hieronder geven we een kort overzicht van onze studie:

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- Indien u meer informatie wenst of vragen heeft over deze studie, kan u terecht bij het onderzoeksteam:
 - o Emilie Bossens (email: emilie.bossens@kuleuven.be)
 - o Prof. dr. Leen d'Haenens (email: leen.dhaenens@kuleuven.be)

Wij verzoeken u vriendelijk de volgende informatie zorgvuldig te lezen. **Door dit document te ondertekenen bevestigt u dat u het volgende begrijpt en ermee akkoord gaat:**

- Ik heb de informatiebrief voor dit onderzoek gelezen en de inhoud ervan volledig begrepen.
- Ik geef mijn toestemming voor de deelname van mijn kind aan dit onderzoeksproject.
- Ik begrijp dat deelname aan dit project vrijwillig is en dat het mogelijk is om op elk moment van deelname af te zien.
- Ik sta toe dat de gegevens van mijn kind worden bewaard en gebruikt in toekomstig onderzoek binnen het ySKILLS-project.
- Ik begrijp dat de anonieme gegevens van dit onderzoek kunnen worden gepubliceerd in academische publicaties, gedeeld in een open archief.

Als u het eens bent met de inhoud, zet dan uw handtekening onderaan dit formulier, voeg een datum toe en stuur het naar ons terug via e-mail naar emilie.bossens@kuleuven.be

De naam van mijn kind: _____

Mijn naam: _____

Datum: _____

Mijn handtekening: _____

